

OPTIMIZING SERVICE MANAGEMENT IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY

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Abstract: *Theoretical and methodological problems of various aspects of tourism development are studied in the economic literature. Theoretical and practical questions on special problems of socio-economic relations of tourism development are reflected in scientific works and researches of scientists from far and near foreign countries. In this article, the issues of development of the tourism sector in Uzbekistan, the reform of the tourism infrastructure, the possibilities of expanding financial investments and similar issues are considered.*

Key words: *tourism, infrastructure, structure, state program, finance, tourist*

INTRODUCTION

In accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev on measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, tourism has been designated as a strategic branch of the economy of our country. The creation of the tourism development committee and its regional structures, the increase of state units, the introduction of tourism departments and offices in the regions, the positions of deputy governors, and the fact that the opportunities for managing this sector have been further expanded have opened a new stage for the development of the tourism sector.

Tourism should be used on a large scale. The development of this sector ensures not only income, but also the opening of new jobs. Taking this into account, the head of state said: If we want to create jobs due to tourism, we need to create conditions for tourists, not conditions.

Today, comprehensive measures are being implemented in the country to develop tourism as one of the strategic industries that diversify the national economy, rapidly develop regions, create new jobs, increase the income and living standards of the population, and increase the country's investment attractiveness. Visa liberalization, simplifying the registration procedure of foreign citizens, providing privileges and preferences for the development of the tourism network made it possible to effectively promote the potential of national tourism in domestic and foreign markets.

First of all, creating favorable conditions for the development of tourism in the private sector, increasing the competitiveness and quality of the services provided, actively and comprehensively promoting the national tourism product in the world market, all this is in accordance with the tasks defined in the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 .

LITERATURE REVIEW

The nature and content of the tourism market and its infrastructure, programs, subjects of the tourism industry, principles of tourism development, mechanisms of regulation of the tourism market, restaurant and hotel companies, scientific bases of problems related to the policy implemented in the tourism sector Zorin I.V, Kvartalnov V.A. [10], Pardaev M.Q. [9], Birzhakov M.B. [3], Beklaryan L.A., Pshennikov A.S. [4], Morozov M.A. [7], Tukhliiev I.S., Hayitboev R., Safarov B.Sh., Tursunova G.R. researched in his works

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY AND EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS

The sustainable development of the regional economy is often determined by the development of the social sphere and the tourism network. Accordingly, currently tourism as a leading branch of national economies has a significant share in the sustainable development of certain countries. The tourism sector is becoming an important factor in the development of human potential. Therefore, it is reflected in the creation of new jobs in a particular country or region, the attraction of additional investments, the increase in tax revenues, the preservation and rational use of cultural, historical and natural resources.

In the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis, "We will continue consistent reforms in the development of tourism in

2021. Special attention is paid to the development of pilgrimage tourism and domestic tourism. Also, 1 trillion soums will be allocated from the budget for the improvement of land areas, water and road infrastructures around tourism facilities. This makes it necessary to develop proposals and recommendations on the directions of its development, while researching the scientific-methodical and practical aspects of the elements and functions of the regional tourism infrastructure.

RESULTS

The organizational-economic and organizational management structures of the tourist services market infrastructure in Uzbekistan are as follows. State administration structures at the national level:

- The State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan: this committee implements the policy in the market of tourist services as a subject of the state;
- Ministry of physical education and sports of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- The Ministry of Justice and the Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan: controls the visa procedure for the entry of foreign tourists;
- state educational institutions: education, training, retraining and upgrading of personnel in the field of tourism.

Public organizations at the national level: Social Tourism Association was established in order to cover all categories of tourists and create suitable conditions for them. This association unites individuals who want to contribute to the development of tourism in Uzbekistan and direct their efforts to the development of social tourism, including the organization of trips for children, young people, the elderly, as well as citizens with disabilities. . At the same time, it establishes cooperation relations with foreign similar associations on the development of inclusive tourism.

The development of tourism infrastructure has a direct impact on the socio-economic development of the regions. The development of tourism cannot be realized without the development of entrepreneurship in this area.

2019-2025 in years Uzbekistan in the Republic tourism field development The concept done increase purposeful indicators

T/r	Indicatorsname	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
1.	to Uzbekistan visit commanding foreign tourists the number (thousand person)	4,800	5,889.9	6 302.2	6 743.3	7 282.8	7 865.4	8 494.7	9,089.3
2.	Tourism services export (mln USA dollars)	951	1 166.9	1 271.9	1 399.1	1 553	1 739.4	1 965.5	2 232.8
3.	Internal tourists the number(thousand visit)	14,000	15,640	17 230	18,806	20 317	21 867	23 404	25,010
4.	Hotels and so on placing number of tools(piece)	910	1 098	1609	2 394	2 562	2 715	2 851	2 994
5.	Placement in the means number of rooms (thousand)	22.0	24	33.7	48.7	52.1	55.2	58.0	60.9
6.	Placement in the means number of seats (thousand)	47.8	52.5	73.6	105.9	113.3	120.1	126.1	132.4
7.	Tour operator the number (person)	957	1 053	1 158	1 262	1 325	1 458	1 531	1 676

First of all, for the development of tourism, it is necessary to build tourism infrastructure facilities, or to provide the promising area with infrastructure, and then to attract tourists there. Of course, this issue is often controversial. Entrepreneurship in the field should initially take into account two main aspects - innovation and risk, which require evaluation. First of all, it is necessary to solve the problems related to capital investments directed to infrastructure and to assess the level of its development and the rate of possible risk.

CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The increase in the effectiveness of tourism programs is determined by the following circumstances: It is necessary to ensure that the achieved level of financial results of the tourist enterprise is higher than the level achieved by competitors according to this indicator. For the sustainable development of the tourist enterprise in the future, it is necessary to ensure that the growth of its financial results is higher than the results achieved by competitors.

Developing a strategy for diversifying tourist products to meet the needs of tourists increases the competitiveness of enterprises in the tourism market.

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